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6GSNS

TrialsNet: TRials supported by Smart Networks beyond 5G

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www.trialsnet.eu

PRESENTING TRIALSNET

Smart Cities have already attracted attention as one of the possible solutions to improve “livability” and people’s quality of life. Beyond 5G and 6G are candidate technologies to positively impact aspects of immense social value as sustainability, resilience, inclusion, trust, security, etc.

TrialsNet vision is to enable the realization of compelling societal values through the implementation of 5G and beyond applications, which will be propaedeutic for the transition towards the next generation of mobile networks. Based on this, TrialsNet will deploy full large-scale trials to implement a heterogenous and comprehensive set of innovative 6G applications based on various technologies such as Cobots, Metaverse, massive twinning, Internet of Senses, and others, covering the three relevant domains of the urban ecosystems in Europe identified as i) Infrastructure, Transportation, Security & Safety, ii) eHealth & Emergency, and iii) Culture, Tourism & Entertainment”.

This future ecosystem is on course to be more collaborative and inclusive than previous generations of network, and TrialsNet aims to lead the way by promoting open architectures, large experimentation sites and taking a multi-stakeholder approach with the objective to connect the digital with the physical and natural worlds. TrialsNet will propose technological innovations towards real-life services in the communication area, to enable Europe to achieve a leading position also in the standardization process (e.g., 3GPP and ETSI) thus securing a leading position for Europe in the global ICT market over the coming years.

Thanks to its activities, TrialsNet will contribute to Europe’s technological leadership in communication technologies and in future emerging enabling technologies, by strengthening European capacities in key parts of future services.

TRIALSNET TEAM

The TrialsNet consortium includes 22 partners from 5 different EU countries (Italy, Greece, Spain, Romania, Belgium) and 1 partner from UK as associated partner representing a variety of verticals, network operators, technology providers, network infrastructure providers, academia, and expertise on business analysis and project management. The project is coordinated by Ericsson Italy while the technical management is led by TIM.

FIRST PROJECT MILESTONE

The first project milestone was met in time, by submitting 4 public deliverables as scheduled. In particular, the detailed definition of use cases (use case design, service, and network requirements, and underlying technologies with software and hardware dependencies), is successfully finalized for all use case domains tackled within the TrialsNet project: 1) Infrastructure, Transportation and Security & Safety (ITSS) domain, 2) eHealth and Emergency (eHE) domain, and 3) Culture, Tourism, and Entertainment (CTE) domain. Such work is presented in deliverables D3.1, D4.1, and D5.1 respectively. Based on the use case requirements, the initial network and platform solutions have been identified for the use case trialing activities, and as such, presented in D2.1. The solutions are based on TrialsNet technologies (baseline and advanced 5G technologies) and platform and network infrastructure that will be designed, deployed, and integrated for the implementation of the trials in the four clusters located in Italy, Spain, Romania, and Greece. In addition, ethics issues related to the project activities have been addressed and reported in 6 deliverables.

SNS JU LUNCH TIME WEBINAR

TrialsNet participated in the 1st SNS JU Lunch Time Webinar, as Silvia Provvedi, project Coordinator, presented the project. Silvia introduced the project objectives, the methodology, and the project plans for the [Open Call](#). You can find more information on the webinar series, including the slides presented by Silvia, on the [SNS JU Website](#). The presentation video is available on [YouTube](#).

TrialsNet also participated to SNS JU questionnaire providing information about the planned work, the challenges being addressed and the expected outcomes of the project. Additionally, the project partners contributed to the SNS Consultation 2023 on WGs establishment.

TRIALSNET AT EUCNC 2023 & 6G SUMMIT

TrialsNet strongly participated at the [EuCNC 2023 & 6G Summit](#), which took place in Gothenburg, on June 6th to 9th, 2023. The project stand was honored by the visit of Peter O'Donohue (Director for the Future Networks Directorate of DG CONNECT, European Commission) and Chiara Mazzone (Programme Officer at Smart Networks and Services Joint Undertaking SNS JU). As part of the dissemination

material, the project prepared a [video](#), that is also available on YouTube. The project's TM Alessandro Trogolo has been [interviewed](#) as the project representative, to explain more about our work and the project goals and achievements. Three Use Case demos have been

presented to our booth visitors: UC2 “Public Infrastructure Assets Management” ([demo](#)), UC6 “Mass Casualty Incident (MCI) and Emergency Rescue in Populated Areas” ([demo](#)), and UC10 “Immersive Fan Engagement”. A video on UC4 “Smart Traffic Management” was also presented. Videos are available on [YouTube](#).

TRIALSNET AT NATIONAL AND INTERNATIONAL EVENTS

The project participated to different international events, in this first semester of activity, including the [Passenger Terminal EXPO](#) in Amsterdam, where we discussed the project approach for developing 5G in airports, and a glimpse from the future for Beyond 5G (B5G) and 6G use cases for Airports. TrialsNet was presented at the [UAIC 2023 summer school](#) and at the [Cluj Innovation Days 2023](#).

DESIGN THINKING PLUS WORKSHOPS

In order to co-design Turin experience together with the project stakeholders and end-users, starting on May the 3rd 2023, at the Casa delle Tecnologie Emergenti di Torino/House of Emerging Technologies of Turin - CTE NEXT, a series of design thinking workshops was held. Design thinking is an innovative approach to interactive brainstorming, combining creativity, empathy, and logic to find innovative solutions to problems, involving users. The first round had as target heterogeneous profiles selected by the University of Turin and Politecnico of Turin. Participants defined the requirements of the two use cases targeting cultural context in Turin: XR diffused experience in museums, and city parks in the metaverse. At the same time, police forces and other stakeholders co-designed the safety and security use case named Control Room in Metaverse. Further info on the [Torino City Lab newsletter](#).

PROJECT INFO AND DISSEMINATION

If you are looking for further info about the project structure, consortium, the different use cases, as well as news and contacts, the [project website](#) is the place to go. The deliverables describing the project use cases (i.e., D3.1, D4.1, and D5.1) and the platform and network solutions (D2.1) have been published on the corresponding [website section](#). A specific section hosts all the info concerning the [Open Call](#).

SkyTG24 presented a piece of [news](#) about the project, explaining the UCs in the Pisa Cluster. The article highlights how the UCs aim at bringing innovation out of the laboratories and at using it to improve everyday life, as well as how the network infrastructure should evolve to support it, describing the main challenges for research and innovation.

OPEN CALL LAUNCH IN OCTOBER!

TrialsNet invites European third parties such as verticals, companies (including SMEs), research centers or any other relevant entity as well as facilities and infrastructure owners, to participate in its large-scale trials activities through the implementation of additional, diversified, and heterogeneous vertical use cases, to support (i) the deployment of new trials on the project's platform and network solutions, as well as (ii) the extension of its infrastructure

domain in other geographical locations in Europe (complementing the main clusters). By applying to the Open Call, third parties could enter in TrialsNet project receiving up to 200.000 € per applicant or up to 300.000 € for multiple-applicant, for a total available budget of 5.580.900. The Open Call will be launched the 16th of October 2023. Further details are available [here](#).

FOLLOW US!

 Project website: <https://trialsnet.eu/>

 LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/trialsnet>

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